

REPORT ON THE BUSINESS MODELLING WORKSHOP IN SALAR (GRANADA)

Summary and action plan regarding the topics discussed
during the meeting on 15 January 2026

1. Introduction

The aim of the meeting held in Salar on **15 January 2026**, which took place in the plenary hall of the Town Hall, was to bring together neighbors interested in the management of the municipality's cultural heritage. During the day meeting, **key concepts such as heritage communities, participatory governance of cultural heritage and cultural business models** were presented, as well as their conception and specific application to the local context of Salar. The event was jointly facilitated by the University of Granada (MEMOLab UGR), Copenhagen Business School and Salar Town Hall.

The workshop was attended by 33 people with different profiles, including various local businesses, tour guides, the parish, tourist accommodation providers, the traders' association, etc. The workshop included a theoretical introduction, analysis of case studies, and work in groups to discuss the strengths and weaknesses of tourism in Salar, both currently and in the near future, design business models and present ideas, concluding with conclusions and steps to be taken.

This initiative is part of the [SECReTour](#) project, which focuses on the protection and enhancement of cultural heritage in rural areas of Europe through the implementation of sustainable tourism business models that promote the socio-economic development of these communities. The University of Granada, leader of the project, is coordinating the pilot in Salar, which aims to explore how participatory approaches and cultural business models can contribute to strengthening local identity, encouraging neighborhood participation and generating sustainable economic opportunities linked to the municipality's cultural heritage.

2. Results of the SWOT analysis

Attached are the results of the SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analyses for the present time and in two years' time (to establish ideas and proposals for the short and medium term).

Results of the Workshop on Alternative Business Models for Sustainable Tourism in Salar (Granada)

SWOT ANALYSIS (PRESENT DAY)

STRENGTHS

- **Strong community engagement** and high levels of social capital.
- **Significant** cultural and architectural **heritage**.
- **Prestige and recognition associated with the Roman villa** as a key element of local identity and attraction.
- **Rich living cultural traditions** (Carnival, Livestock Fair, Holy Week, etc.).
- A strong and well-defined **community identity**.
- **Privileged geographical location**.
- A **landscape of high cultural and environmental value**, with strong potential for the development of cultural routes.
- **A Long-term heritage project**.
- **Effective collaboration** with neighbouring municipalites.

WEAKNESSES

- **Mistrust** of the project among the local population due to limit access to clear and direct information.
- **Uncertainty** regarding the management, accessibility and public use of the heritage site.
- A **poorly defined tourism model** with limit differentiation.
- **An insufficient tourism offer**, particularly in traditional gastronomy and nature-based tourism.
- **Lack of basic infrastructure** to support visits the Roman villa.
- **Limited generational renewal** and insufficient support for youth entrepreneurship.

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- Development of **hostels and guesthouses**.
- **Growing interest in cultural tourism**.
- **Sustainable use** of natural resources and cultural heritage.
- Salar's **favourable geographical location**.
- **A rich combination of heritage, landscape, and gastronomy**.
- Promotion of **new business initiatives**.
- **Encouragement of active community involvement**.
- Organisation of **workshops and training activities** by the Town Council.
- **Revaluation and revitalisation** of the rural environment.
- **Depopulation** viewed as an **opportunity** for new development projects.
- The village positioned as an **attractive place** for young people to live.
- Renovation of vacant houses as **tourist accommodation** managed by local associations.

OPORTUNITIES

- **Lack** of hostels and accommodations
- **Competition** form rival destinations
- **Limited involvement** of local population
- Ongoing **depopulation** process
- **Risk of excessive and poorly managed tourism**.
- **Dependence on tour operators focused on mass tourism**.
- **Insufficient local services**.
- Shortage of rental housing.
- **Lack of training** in the tourism sector.
- **Insufficient training and awareness-raising** in schools and families.
- **Low levels of motivation** among young people.

THREATS

Results of the Workshop on Alternative Business Models for Sustainable Tourism in Salar (Granada)

SWOT ANALYSIS (IN TWO YEARS)

STRENGTHS

- **A Roman villa of outstanding significance** and in a good state of conservation.
- **High** heritage, cultural, and social **value**.
- **Strategic location** within Salar's heritage framework and an attractive cultural environment.
- **Strong potential for sustainable tourism** and an increase in visitor numbers.
- Development of **longer and more in-depth** guided tours.
- Capacity for social participation and interaction with local groups and stakeholders.
- Use of social media for **dissemination and promotion**.

WEAKNESSES

- **Lack of an effective communication and coordination network** between the Roman villa and the rest of the heritage assets.
- **Poor access to the Roman Villa of Salar**.
- **Insufficient infrastructure for visitor services** and site management.
- **Limited consolidation** of the site as a tourist destination.
- **Weak transport links and hospitality services** in the surrounding area.
- **Population decline and demographic scarcity**.
- **Lack of tourism diversification**.
- **Weak integration with other cultural activities** in the surrounding area.

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- Optimisation of **existing resources** through **local associations** and training actions oriented towards sustainable growth.
- **Development of complementary activities** linked to hospitality, guided services, and accommodation.
- **Increased awareness among the local population** of the value of Salar's cultural and heritage resources.
- **Attraction of external investment** to improve infrastructure, services, and facilities.
- Creation of **green pedestrian access routes** between Salar and the Roman villa, promoting sustainable mobility and enhancing the visitor experience.
- Strengthening opportunities related to accommodation, gastronomy, crafts, and local traditions.
- **Expansion and diversification** of the range of cultural activities linked to the Roman villa.
- **Greater flexibility in opening hours** for group visits as an opportunity to increase and diversify demand.

OPPORTUNITIES

- **Insufficient physical resources** at the interpretation centre, limiting its operation and capacity as a cultural space.
- **Lack of accessibility** both at the Roman villa and within the town of Salar.
- **Scarcity of activities aimed at specific target audiences** interested in the Villa and the town, reducing demand diversification.
- Dependence on a **single access route** or main road, with connectivity and wayfinding issues.
- Risk that existing strengths, if not improved and updated, may become threats in the medium term.
- **Limitations in available payment methods** at the Roman villa.

THREATS

3. Action plan

This table summarises the ideas, key actions and possible actors for implementing the proposals to a greater or lesser extent in the coming months and years.

Proposal	Key actions	Actors
1. Heritage integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a coordination network between heritage sites - Design cultural itineraries - Integrate archaeological sites into tourism narratives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Town hall - Department of Culture - Local associations - Tourist guides - Neighboring municipalities
2. Access and infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve roads and access to the Roman villa of Salar - Signposting routes - Assess parking - Install information points and services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Town hall - Provincial Council - Construction companies - Local volunteers
3. Social activation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness campaigns - Participatory workshops - Involving communities and young people in heritage and tourism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local associations - Educational centres - Cultural centres - Local youth - Cultural associations
4. Tourism diversification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create comprehensive tourism products: visits, gastronomy, crafts, nature - Promote accommodation - Design packages for long stays 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local businesses - Hoteliers - Artisans - Agencies - Town hall - Cultural associations - GDR <i>Poniente Granadino</i>
5. Communication and visibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve digital presence - Promote the villa and events - Create promotional materials - Facilitate online bookings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tourist office - Digital companies - Local media

6. Entrepreneurship and generational renewal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training and support for young people - Encouraging cultural and gastronomic entrepreneurship - Intergenerational training - Promoting collective projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Town council Youth council - Local associations - Chambers of commerce - <i>Poniente Granadino</i> Development Group
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4. Additional resources and case studies in Spain and Europe

The following is a description of the cases presented during the workshop, selected for their relevance to rural and heritage contexts such as Salar.

These cases are examples of good practices at the European level and show a diversity of approaches to the active role that residents, businesses and local administrations can play in heritage management. They also present proposals for alternative business models in cultural tourism that could be adapted to the context of Salar.

I. Taula del Sénia Community and Sénia Territory Association (Valencia-Catalonia-Aragon, Spain)

Created in 2006, the Community is a network of 27 municipalities. They share similar characteristics (history, culture and language), but also similar problems (income level, depopulation and ageing population). At the administrative level, it is a meeting point for local councils. In addition, the Community, together with local businesses and olive tree owners in the area, form the Sénia Territory Association.

This group manages projects related to the area's ancient olive trees, an incomparable heritage, and develops activities such as an inventory of ancient olive trees, olive oil tourism, exhibitions and conferences, and the development and certification of local businesses related to olive oil production.

Relevant links: <https://www.tauladelsenia.es/es>

<https://www.cultura.gob.es/libro-verde-patrimonio/buenas-practicas-todas/taulasenia.html>

II. 4theRegion, For the region (Swansea Bay, Wales)

4theRegion is an organisation created in 2019 that brings together local businesses, neighborhood associations, universities, NGOs and local councils from the same region. It is an alliance formed with the main objective of ensuring the well-being and sustainability of the region, where local people discuss issues that affect them all, such as tourism, youth employment and the management of public resources.

Its main activities include meetings, workshops and participatory activities that serve to share ideas, improve coordination and learn from each other.

Relevant links: <https://www.4theregion.org.uk/>

III. Comuniterràe (Terre di Mezzo, Piedmont, Italy)

Comuniterràe is a participatory cultural project that brings together ten municipalities in the "Terre di Mezzo", an area located between the valley floor and the mountainous areas within the Parco Nazionale della Val Grande in the Piedmont region (northern Italy). Launched in January 2017 by the Associazione Ars.Uni.Vco together with the Parco Nazionale Val Grande, and with the support of the Regione Piemonte and the Fondazione Comunitaria del VCO, the project stems from the development of community maps built collectively with local residents. These maps include not only places and material heritage assets, but also traditions, historical photographs, memories and stories that reflect the shared identity of local communities, and have been collected in an accessible digital archive as a tool for enhancing the cultural heritage of the area.

Building on this participatory work, Comuniterràe has moved towards the creation of an ecomuseum, a concept of a 'living museum' that is not limited to collections in enclosed spaces, but integrates natural, historical and cultural spaces spread across the territory and emphasises the active participation of the local population in the interpretation and management of their heritage. The project has incorporated digital technologies such as QR code plaques at points of interest, which allow visitors and residents to easily access stories, archives and contextual content about these places.

Relevant links: <https://www.comuniterrae.it/>

<https://www.instagram.com/comuniterrae/>

IV. La Paranza Cooperative (Naples, Italy)

The La Paranza Cooperative, founded in 2006 in Naples, is a social enterprise aimed at restoring and promoting the catacombs of San Gennaro and San Gaudioso, located in areas traditionally outside the city's tourist circuits. The project was created with the aim of using cultural heritage as a tool for local development and improving the socio-economic conditions of the neighborhood.

Its model is based on training and employing unemployed young people from the area as tourist guides, so that the profits generated by the tourist activity

directly benefit the local community. The cooperative works in close collaboration with the city council, the parish and other businesses in the neighborhood, creating an integrated tourist offer that exemplifies a cultural business model based on cooperation between local actors.

Relevant links: <https://catacombedinapoli.it/en/about/>

<https://www.europeanheritageawards.eu/winners/la-paranza-cooperative/>

V. Camping equipment rental Iceland (Reykjavík, Iceland)

The camping equipment rental service in Reykjavík (Iceland), a product-service model, was established in 2011 and emerged in response to an unmet need in the country: the high cost and inconvenience for visitors of purchasing quality equipment for nature tourism. The model also seeks to reduce the environmental impact associated with the purchase, breakage or abandonment of equipment in natural parks and protected areas.

The company offers camping and outdoor activity equipment rentals from different brands, with rates adapted to the duration of the rental and the number of products contracted. It also collaborates with tourism agencies and other operators in the country to offer integrated services, contributing both to a more sustainable tourism experience and to the development of the local economy.

Relevant links: <https://www.iceland-camping-equipment.com/>

VI. Km 0 and tourism (Es Pla, Mallorca, Spain)

The km 0 local product initiative in Pla de Mallorca is promoted by the Mancomunitat del Pla de Mallorca in collaboration with agricultural producers, restaurants and the tourism sector, as part of its tourism sustainability strategy. This strategy seeks to establish alliances between the primary sector and tourism stakeholders to integrate local products into the destination's gastronomic and experiential offering, while strengthening the local economy and cultural values of the region.

To this end, actions have been developed such as km 0 product workshops that bring together producers and tourism companies, and the creation of promotional tools such as digital catalogues that showcase local products and producers. The km 0 product is presented as a key component of the Pla's tourism identity, promoting gastronomic experiences based on traditional ingredients and techniques, as well as collaboration between farmers, restaurateurs and tourism services.

Relevant links: <https://km0plademallorca.com/>

<https://www.segittur.es/ods-y-sostenibilidad/proyectos-sostenibilidad/guia-de-innovacion-en-agroturismo-12-casos-de-exito/>

VII. Vinarós Gastronómico (Vinarós, Castellón, Spain)

In Vinaròs, Vinaròs prawns have become an iconic gastronomic product and a central element of the municipality's tourism strategy. Promoted by the Vinaròs Town Council, in collaboration with fish producers, restaurateurs and the local association Vinaròs Gastronòmic, this initiative seeks to position prawns as a symbol of local identity and as a driving force for gastronomic tourism.

To boost this strategy, regular gastronomic activities and events are organised, such as the Prawn Cuisine Days, the Prawn Gastro Festival and the National Prawn Cuisine Competition in Vinaròs, which bring together restaurants, chefs and the general public around creative and traditional culinary proposals with prawns as the central theme. These events are promoted by the local council and encourage local restaurants to commit to using local produce, thereby strengthening the stable collaboration between producers, the hospitality industry and the tourism sector.

Relevant links: <https://turisme.vinaros.es/es/que-hacer/gastronomia>

Below are additional resources that compile examples of best practices in cultural heritage management and sustainable tourism, developed within the framework of the SECreTour project research.

1. Literature review on emerging literature on cultural heritage management and cultural business models: <https://zenodo.org/records/15254190>
2. Report on the categorisation of cultural models of businesses: <https://zenodo.org/records/15560925>
3. Repository of best practices in cultural tourism: <https://secretourproject.eu/goodpractices>

5. Results of Canvas Business Models

Below are the different business models that were devised by groups during the workshop.

Group 1: ExperienciaSalar

KEY PARTNERS	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSAL	CLIENT/BENEFICIARY RELATION	CLIENT/BENEFICIARY SEGMENTS	
<p>What people, groups or organisations are essential for this to work?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Town Hall - Associations 	<p>What do we offer to people who are interested in our project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Routes (trails, olive mills, acequias) - Cultural facilities (museums...) - Accommodation network 	<p>Why is our project different, what value adds to the town and the tourist?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a personalised experience 	<p>How do we attract, interact with and maintain the relationship with the artist or project beneficiary?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personalised reminders 	<p>What kind of people might be attracted to our project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Families - Groups of friends 	
	<p>KEY RESOURCES</p> <p>What resources does our project have, without which it could not function?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human (2 people) - Cession-convention-town hall - Coordination - Funding - Network of companies 		<p>OUTREACH CHANNELS</p> <p>How do we make ourselves known?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media - Word of mouth 		
<p>EXPENSE STRUCTURE</p>			<p>INCOME SOURCES</p>		
<p>How are we going to spend our money?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experiences with visitors (transport, advertising, services) 			<p>What will generate profits for us?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Income from visitors 		

Group 2: Salar accommodation

KEY PARTNERS	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSAL	CLIENT/BENEFICIARY RELATION	CLIENT/BENEFICIARY SEGMENTS
<p><i>What people, groups or organisations are essential for this to work?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Associate with other accommodations, help each other, network support of the professionals - Whatsapp group - Availability of other municipalities, services 	<p><i>What do we offer to people who are interested in our project?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diverse experiences - Creative workshops - Visits to the region - Late check-out - Hiking 	<p><i>Why is our project different, what value adds to the town and the tourist?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Previous planning of the sites and experiences of interested - Several days packs (2,3,4) - Recommendation of experiences in the area, contacts 	<p><i>How do we attract, interact with and maintain the relationship with the artist or project beneficiary?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personalised experiences - Client support 	<p><i>What kind of people might be attracted to our project?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National tourism - International tourism - Families - Professionals
	<p>KEY RESOURCES</p> <p><i>What resources does our project have, without which it could not function?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality photographs - Good conditions of accommodations - Promotional websites 		<p>OUTREACH CHANNELS</p> <p><i>How do we make ourselves known?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploiting international markets: relevance of languages - Website and social media in different languages (but not only) - Advertising in tourism platforms of countries of origin 	
<p>EXPENSE STRUCTURE</p>			<p>INCOME SOURCES</p>	
<p><i>How are we going to spend our money?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pay accommodation, maintenance - Freelance, salaries, supplies and operational expenses, advertising 			<p><i>What will generate profits for us?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accommodation income 	

Group 3: Salar White Night

KEY PARTNERS	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSAL	CLIENT/BENEFICIARY RELATION	CLIENT/BENEFICIARY SEGMENTS
<p><i>What people, groups or organisations are essential for this to work?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Associations, for example Women Association el Rincón de Venus - Carnival - Entrepreneurs 	<p><i>What do we offer to people who are interested in our project?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Roman dish contest - Live music - Gifts - Shows - Entertainment for children - Roman passacaglia 	<p><i>Why is our project different, what value adds to the town and the tourist?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mix of leisure, hospitality and culture 	<p><i>How do we attract, interact with and maintain the relationship with the artist or project beneficiary?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incentive of 5€ to buy in the event - The visitor can participate and dress up, unique experience 	<p><i>What kind of people might be attracted to our project?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Store clients - Salar neighbors - Potentially attract tourists
	<p>KEY RESOURCES</p> <p><i>What resources does our project have, without which it could not function?</i></p>		<p>OUTREACH CHANNELS</p> <p><i>How do we make ourselves known?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social network - Word of mouth 	
	<p>EXPENSE STRUCTURE</p> <p><i>How are we going to spend our money?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sound (infrastructure) - Children games (Gymkana, greasy pole) 		<p>INCOME SOURCES</p> <p><i>What will generate profits for us?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public funding - Business contribution (direct and indirect) 	

Group 4: Time travel through the lower Genil riverbank

KEY PARTNERS	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSAL	CLIENT/BENEFICIARY RELATION	CLIENT/BENEFICIARY SEGMENTS
<p><i>What people, groups or organisations are essential for this to work?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Town Hall - Rural Development Group Poniente - Cultural associations - Local businesses - Association of businessmen and entrepreneurs of the Community 	<p><i>What do we offer to people who are interested in our project?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get to know the cultural identity - Walk through history - Local cuisine - Traditions - Agriculture 	<p><i>Why is our project different, what value adds to the town and the tourist?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote cooperation - There is no comparable offer currently - Boosts the local economy 	<p><i>How do we attract, interact with and maintain the relationship with the artist or project beneficiary?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer likable immersive experiences and because of that they are publicized - Visits should be made by locals who know traditions and legends 	<p><i>What kind of people might be attracted to our project?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School groups - Expert groups - Senior groups
	<p>KEY RESOURCES</p> <p><i>What resources does our project have, without which it could not function?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural identities; commitment of local councils • Salar: Roman villa, palace (tower), Bañuelo, gastronomy; • Lachar: castle; • Huétor Tajar: tower, tile works, water channel, gastronomy... • Villanueva Mesía: bread mil • Moraleda de Zafayona: Iberian and Roman archaeological site at Cerro de la Mora 		<p>OUTREACH CHANNELS</p> <p><i>How do we make ourselves known?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media - Participation in fairs, forums - Publicity in town halls and Granada's Council 	
EXPENSE STRUCTURE		INCOME SOURCES		

<p><i>How are we going to spend our money?</i></p> <p>feasibility study (financing) advertising, website, social media signage, transport, staff</p>		<p><i>What will generate profits for us?</i></p> <p>- Selling trips and routes - Indirect (breakfast and lunch in hospitality, local shops)</p>
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6. Next steps

- Creation of the Salar Heritage Community and membership
- Creation of a Salar Heritage Community working group
- Design of priorities and strategy for the Salar Heritage Community
- New meetings and working sessions, with the support of MEMOLab UGR and Copenhagen Business School